

A note on some bounds between cubic spline interpolants depending on the boundary conditions: Application to a monotonicity property [☆]

Antonio Baeza ^{*}, Dionisio F. Yáñez

Departament de Matemàtiques, Universitat de València, 46100, Burjassot, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 9 December 2021

Accepted 19 June 2022

Available online 22 June 2022

Keywords:

Cubic spline

Boundary conditions

Order of approximation

Monotonicity

ABSTRACT

In the context of cubic splines, the authors have contributed to a recent paper dealing with the computation of nonlinear derivatives at the interior nodes so that monotonicity is enforced while keeping the order of approximation of the spline as high as possible. During the review process of that paper, one of the reviewers raised the question of whether a cubic spline interpolating monotone data could be forced to preserve monotonicity by imposing suitable values of the first derivative at the endpoints. Albeit a negative answer appears to be intuitive, we have found no results regarding this fact. In this short work we prove that the answer to that question is actually negative.

© 2022 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. on behalf of IMACS. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Approximation techniques are used in applications as design of curves, surfaces, robotics, creation of pieces in industry

In many applications that use approximations of given data by means of smooth curves or surfaces, additional properties like monotonicity and convexity preservation are often required. In particular, interpolation by cubic splines is a well-known technique that provides twice continuously differentiable curves. The problem consists on constructing a piecewise polynomial with equal first and second derivative values at the nodes, so that the interpolant is globally twice continuously differentiable.

In order to solve the problem, values for the first or second derivative at the boundary points are necessary. For natural splines, the values for the second derivative at the endpoints are set to zero, while for interpolating splines first derivative values are forced to coincide with those of the function derivative at the endpoint.

Splines do not preserve data monotonicity and consequently many works have dealt with the problem of monotonicity-preserving spline interpolation, being [3] a seminal paper on the matter.

The authors have participated in a contribution [1] where a monotonicity-preserving reconstruction is proposed using nonlinear reconstructions of the first derivatives at the interior points. During the review process of the paper one of the reviewers raised the following question: *By changing the first derivative at the endpoints of the interval, is it possible to find twice continuously differentiable monotonicity preserving cubic spline interpolants?*

In this note we show that the answer to this question is negative. We first prove a bound on the distance between two splines that interpolate the same data but differ on the values imposed at the boundary. We then show that monotonicity

[☆] Funding: This research has been supported by grant PID2020-117211GB-I00 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033.

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: antonio.baeza@uv.es (A. Baeza), dionisio.yanez@uv.es (D.F. Yáñez).

3. Distance between two spline interpolations with different boundary conditions

In this section we apply Lemma 2.1 to compute a bound on the distance between two splines constructed using different boundary values.

Proposition 3.1. *Let $P(x)$ and $\tilde{P}(x)$ be the cubic spline interpolants of the form (1) for the data $\{x_i, f(x_i), \dot{f}_i\}$ and $\{x_i, f(x_i), \tilde{f}_i\}_{i=1}^n$ respectively, with $\tilde{f}_i = \dot{f}_i$ for $1 < i < n$ (computed by solving system (5)) and $\tilde{f}_i \neq \dot{f}_i$ for $i = 1, n$. For $2 \leq i \leq n - 2$, $P_i(x)$ and $\tilde{P}_i(x)$ denote the corresponding polynomial pieces for each spline. Then the following inequality holds:*

$$|P_i(x) - \tilde{P}_i(x)| \leq 8h_i(2^{-i}\lambda_1|\tilde{f}_1 - \dot{f}_1| + \mu_{n-2}2^{i-n}|\tilde{f}_n - \dot{f}_n|), \quad \forall x \in [x_i, x_{i+1}]. \tag{7}$$

Proof. Let us start calculating

$$b_1 - \tilde{b}_1 = \lambda_1(\tilde{f}_1 - \dot{f}_1), \quad b_i - \tilde{b}_i = 0, \quad 2 \leq i \leq n - 3, \quad b_{n-2} - \tilde{b}_{n-2} = \mu_{n-2}(\tilde{f}_n - \dot{f}_n). \tag{8}$$

Then, for $2 \leq i \leq n - 1$ it holds

$$\dot{f}_i - \tilde{f}_i = \sum_{j=1}^{n-2} A_{i-1,j}^{-1} b_j - \sum_{j=1}^{n-2} A_{i-1,j}^{-1} \tilde{b}_j = \sum_{j=1}^{n-2} A_{i-1,j}^{-1} (b_j - \tilde{b}_j) = A_{i-1,1}^{-1} \lambda_1 (\tilde{f}_1 - \dot{f}_1) + A_{i-1,n-2}^{-1} \mu_{n-2} (\tilde{f}_n - \dot{f}_n). \tag{9}$$

$$(\dot{f}_{i+1} - \tilde{f}_{i+1}) + (\dot{f}_i - \tilde{f}_i) = (A_{i-1,1}^{-1} + A_{i,1}^{-1}) \lambda_1 (\tilde{f}_1 - \dot{f}_1) + (A_{i-1,n-2}^{-1} + A_{i,n-2}^{-1}) \mu_{n-2} (\tilde{f}_n - \dot{f}_n), \quad 2 \leq i \leq n - 2.$$

The distance between $P_i(x)$ and $\tilde{P}_i(x)$ for all $x \in [x_i, x_{i+1}]$, $i = 2, \dots, n - 2$, can be obtained with:

$$\begin{aligned} P_i(x) - \tilde{P}_i(x) &= (\dot{f}_i - \tilde{f}_i)(x - x_i) - (\dot{f}_i - \tilde{f}_i) \frac{(x - x_i)^2}{h_i} + \left((\dot{f}_{i+1} - \tilde{f}_{i+1}) + (\dot{f}_i - \tilde{f}_i) \right) \frac{(x - x_i)^2 (x - x_{i+1})}{h_i^2} \\ &= \lambda_1 (\tilde{f}_1 - \dot{f}_1) (x - x_i) \left(A_{i-1,1}^{-1} + A_{i-1,1}^{-1} \frac{(x - x_i)}{h_i} + (A_{i-1,1}^{-1} + A_{i,1}^{-1}) \frac{(x - x_i)(x - x_{i+1})}{h_i^2} \right) \\ &\quad + \mu_{n-2} (\tilde{f}_n - \dot{f}_n) (x - x_i) \left(A_{i-1,n-2}^{-1} + A_{i-1,n-2}^{-1} \frac{(x - x_i)}{h_i} + (A_{i-1,n-2}^{-1} + A_{i,n-2}^{-1}) \frac{(x - x_i)(x - x_{i+1})}{h_i^2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

From $|A_{i-1,1}^{-1} + A_{i,1}^{-1}| \leq |A_{i-1,1}^{-1}|$, $|A_{i-1,n-2}^{-1} + A_{i,n-2}^{-1}| \leq |A_{i,n-2}^{-1}|$ and $|A_{i-1,n-2}^{-1}| \leq |A_{i,n-2}^{-1}|$, $i = 2, \dots, n - 2$ by Lemma 2.1, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} |P_i(x) - \tilde{P}_i(x)| &\leq \lambda_1 |A_{i-1,1}^{-1}| |\tilde{f}_1 - \dot{f}_1| (x - x_i) \left(1 + \frac{(x - x_i)}{h_i} + \frac{(x - x_i)(x_{i+1} - x)}{h_i^2} \right) \\ &\quad + \mu_{n-2} |A_{i,n-2}^{-1}| |\tilde{f}_n - \dot{f}_n| (x - x_i) \left(1 + \frac{(x - x_i)}{h_i} + \frac{(x - x_i)(x_{i+1} - x)}{h_i^2} \right) \\ &= (\lambda_1 |A_{i-1,1}^{-1}| |\tilde{f}_1 - \dot{f}_1| + \mu_{n-2} |A_{i,n-2}^{-1}| |\tilde{f}_n - \dot{f}_n|) \left((x - x_i) + \frac{(x - x_i)^2}{h_i} + \frac{(x - x_i)^2 (x_{i+1} - x)}{h_i^2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, by Lemma 2.1 it holds $|A_{i-1,1}^{-1}| \leq \frac{8}{3}2^{-i}$ and $|A_{i,n-2}^{-1}| \leq \frac{8}{3}2^{i-n}$. Then:

$$|P_i(x) - \tilde{P}_i(x)| \leq 8h_i(2^{-i}\lambda_1|\tilde{f}_1 - \dot{f}_1| + \mu_{n-2}2^{i-n}|\tilde{f}_n - \dot{f}_n|). \tag{10}$$

As a consequence of Proposition 3.1 we can prove the following result regarding the order of approximation of the spline (known result, showed e.g. in [5]).

Corollary 3.2. *Assume that $\hat{h} < 1$, $f(x) \in C^4([x_1, x_n])$ and let $L > 0$ be such that $|f^{(4)}(x)| \leq L$, for all $x \in [x_1, x_n]$. Let $P(x)$ be the interpolating spline of f and \tilde{P} be another cubic spline constructed with the same data as $P(x)$ except for the first derivative values at the interval endpoints that can take any value. If there exist $K, p > 0$, such that $\hat{h}/h_j \leq K$ for all $j = 1, \dots, n - 1$ and $\Omega := \{i \in \mathbb{N} : -p \log_2(\hat{h}) < i < n + p \log_2(\hat{h})\} \neq \emptyset$ then*

$$\max_{x \in [x_i, x_{i+1}], i \in \Omega} |\tilde{P}_i(x) - f(x)| = O(\hat{h}^{\min\{p+1, 4\}}).$$

Proof. If P is the spline interpolator constructed with the solution of system $A\dot{F} = B$ defined in (5) with clamped boundary conditions $\dot{f}_1 = f'(x_1)$, $\dot{f}_n = f'(x_n)$ then it is known [6] that

$$\max_{x \in [x_i, x_{i+1}]} |P_i(x) - f(x)| = O(\hat{h}^4).$$

On the other hand, $i \in \Omega$ implies $2^{-i} < \hat{h}^p$ and $2^{n-i} < \hat{h}^p$. The result hence follows from Proposition 3.1.

4. Main result

In this section we show that given a cubic spline that does not preserve data monotonicity, is it not always possible to obtain another cubic spline that does by only changing the first derivative at the endpoints. We recall following theorem [3]:

Theorem 4.1. (Necessary conditions for monotonicity.) Let P_i be a monotone cubic Hermite interpolant of the data $\{(x_i, f_i, \dot{f}_i), (x_{i+1}, f_{i+1}, \dot{f}_{i+1})\}$. Then:

$$\text{sign}(\dot{f}_i) = \text{sign}(\dot{f}_{i+1}) = \text{sign}(m_i). \tag{11}$$

Furthermore, if $m_i = 0$ then P_i is monotone (constant) if and only if $\dot{f}_i = \dot{f}_{i+1} = 0$.

We prove the main proposition of the paper.

Proposition 4.2. Let n be an odd number and $\{(x_i, f_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, with $f_1 \leq f_2 \leq \dots \leq f_n$ be the data used to construct a spline P by solving the system given in Eq. (5) with given boundary data \dot{f}_1, \dot{f}_n which satisfies:

- P is monotone in $[x_1, x_2]$ and $[x_{n-1}, x_n]$.
- There exists $i_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ with $\max(1, 1 - \log_2(R_1)) \leq i_0 < \min(n - 2, n - 3 + \log_2(R_n))$ such that $P_{i_0}(x_{i_0+\frac{1}{2}}) - f_{i_0+1} > 0$, being

$$x_{i_0+\frac{1}{2}} = x_{i_0} + \frac{h_{i_0}}{2}, R_1 = \frac{P_{i_0}(x_{i_0+\frac{1}{2}}) - f_{i_0+1}}{8K_1\lambda_1} \text{ with}$$

$$K_1 = 3(A_{1,1}^{-1}(\lambda_1 m_1 + \mu_1 m_2) + A_{1,n-2}^{-1}(\lambda_{n-2} m_{n-2} + \mu_{n-2} m_{n-1})) + \sum_{j=2}^{n-3} A_{1,j}^{-1} b_j + 4m_1,$$

$$\text{and } R_n = \frac{P_{i_0}(x_{i_0+\frac{1}{2}}) - f_{i_0+1}}{8\mu_{n-2} K_n} \text{ with}$$

$$K_n = 3(A_{n-2,1}^{-1}(\lambda_1 m_1 + \mu_1 m_2) + A_{n-2,n-2}^{-1}(\lambda_{n-2} m_{n-2} + \mu_{n-2} m_{n-1})) + \sum_{j=2}^{n-3} A_{n-2,j}^{-1} b_j + 4m_{n-1}.$$

If a new spline \tilde{P} is constructed with the same data as P but changing the values \dot{f}_1 and \dot{f}_n by \tilde{f}_1 and \tilde{f}_n then \tilde{P} is not monotone in $[x_1, x_2]$ or $[x_{n-1}, x_n]$ or $(\tilde{P}_{i_0}(x_{i_0+\frac{1}{2}}) - f_{i_0+1}) > 0$, i.e., the new spline is not monotone.

Proof. As $f_1 \leq \dots \leq f_n$, in order to obtain a monotone spline we have that any approximation to the first derivative at any node has to be higher or equal to 0 by Theorem 4.1. By Lemma 2.1 it holds $A_{1,1}^{-1}, A_{1,n-2}^{-1} > 0$ since n is an odd number. Thus, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{f}_2 &= \sum_{j=1}^{n-2} A_{1,j}^{-1} b_j = A_{1,1}^{-1} b_1 + A_{1,n-2}^{-1} b_{n-2} + \sum_{j=2}^{n-3} A_{1,j}^{-1} b_j \\ &= A_{1,1}^{-1} (3(\lambda_1 m_1 + \mu_1 m_2) - \lambda_1 \dot{f}_1) + A_{1,n-2}^{-1} (3(\lambda_{n-2} m_{n-2} + \mu_{n-2} m_{n-1}) - \mu_{n-2} \dot{f}_n) + \sum_{j=2}^{n-3} A_{1,j}^{-1} b_j \\ &\leq 3(A_{1,1}^{-1}(\lambda_1 m_1 + \mu_1 m_2) + A_{1,n-2}^{-1}(\lambda_{n-2} m_{n-2} + \mu_{n-2} m_{n-1})) + \sum_{j=2}^{n-3} A_{1,j}^{-1} b_j =: k_1 \end{aligned}$$

As P_1 is monotone in $[x_1, x_2]$ then

$$f_1 \leq P_1(x_{1+\frac{1}{2}}) = \frac{f_1 + f_2}{2} + \frac{h_1}{8} (\dot{f}_1 - \dot{f}_2) \leq f_2 \Rightarrow \dot{f}_2 + 4 \left(\frac{f_1 - f_2}{h_1} \right) \leq \dot{f}_1 \leq \dot{f}_2 + 4 \left(\frac{f_2 - f_1}{h_1} \right) \Rightarrow 0 \leq \dot{f}_1 \leq \dot{f}_2 + 4m_1 \leq k_1 + 4m_1 =: K_1$$

Analogously:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{f}_{n-1} &= \sum_{j=1}^{n-2} A_{n-2,j}^{-1} b_j = A_{n-2,1}^{-1} b_1 + A_{n-2,n-2}^{-1} b_{n-2} + \sum_{j=2}^{n-3} A_{n-2,j}^{-1} b_j \\ &= A_{n-2,1}^{-1} (3(\lambda_1 m_1 + \mu_1 m_2) - \lambda_1 \dot{f}_1) + A_{n-2,n-2}^{-1} (3(\lambda_{n-2} m_{n-2} + \mu_{n-2} m_{n-1}) - \mu_{n-2} \dot{f}_n) + \sum_{j=2}^{n-3} A_{n-2,j}^{-1} b_j \\ &\leq 3(A_{n-2,1}^{-1} (\lambda_1 m_1 + \mu_1 m_2) + A_{n-2,n-2}^{-1} (\lambda_{n-2} m_{n-2} + \mu_{n-2} m_{n-1})) + \sum_{j=2}^{n-3} A_{n-2,j}^{-1} b_j =: k_n, \end{aligned}$$

as P_{n-1} is monotone in $[x_{n-1}, x_n]$ then

$$\begin{aligned} f_{n-1} \leq P_{n-1}(x_{n-\frac{1}{2}}) &= \frac{f_{n-1} + f_n}{2} + \frac{h_{n-1}}{8} (\dot{f}_{n-1} - \dot{f}_n) \leq f_n \\ \Rightarrow \dot{f}_{n-1} + 4 \left(\frac{f_{n-1} - f_n}{h_{n-1}} \right) &\leq \dot{f}_n \leq \dot{f}_{n-1} + 4 \left(\frac{f_n - f_{n-1}}{h_{n-1}} \right) \\ \Rightarrow 0 \leq \dot{f}_n \leq \dot{f}_{n-1} + 4m_{n-1} &\leq k_n + 4m_{n-1} =: K_n. \end{aligned}$$

The same argument applies to any spline \tilde{P} that is monotone in $[x_1, x_2]$ and $[x_{n-1}, x_n]$ and then the same conditions have to be satisfied by \tilde{P} i.e. $0 \leq \tilde{f}_1 \leq K_1$, $0 \leq \tilde{f}_n \leq K_n$. By hypothesis we know that there exists $i_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $P_{i_0}(x_{i_0+\frac{1}{2}}) - f_{i_0+1} > 0$, thus:

$$\frac{f_{i_0} + f_{i_0+1}}{2} + \frac{h_{i_0}}{8} (\dot{f}_{i_0} - \dot{f}_{i_0+1}) = P_{i_0}(x_{i_0+\frac{1}{2}}) > f_{i_0+1}.$$

We take

$$\varepsilon := P_{i_0}(x_{i_0+\frac{1}{2}}) - f_{i_0+1} = \frac{f_{i_0} - f_{i_0+1}}{2} + \frac{h_{i_0}}{8} (\dot{f}_{i_0} - \dot{f}_{i_0+1}) > 0$$

and by Lemma 2.1, from $1 - \log_2(R_1) \leq i_0 < n - 2$ and $n - 3 \geq i_0 - \log_2(R_n)$ we obtain:

$$|A_{i_0,1}^{-1}| \leq \frac{2}{3} \cdot 2^{-|i_0-1|} \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{12\lambda_1 K_1}, \quad |A_{i_0+1,n-2}^{-1}| \leq \frac{2}{3} \cdot 2^{-|n-3-i_0|} \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{12\mu_{n-2} K_n}.$$

If we denote as $\tilde{f}_{i_0}, \tilde{f}_{i_0+1}$ the new values obtained by changing the first derivative values \dot{f}_1 and \dot{f}_n by \tilde{f}_1 and \tilde{f}_n , then, according to (9) the distance with the original derivative approximation is:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{f}_{i_0} - \dot{f}_{i_0} &= A_{i_0,1}^{-1} \lambda_1 (f'_1 - \tilde{f}_1) + A_{i_0,n-2}^{-1} \mu_{n-2} (f'_n - \tilde{f}_n); \\ \tilde{f}_{i_0+1} - \dot{f}_{i_0+1} &= A_{i_0+1,1}^{-1} \lambda_1 (f'_1 - \tilde{f}_1) + A_{i_0+1,n-2}^{-1} \mu_{n-2} (f'_n - \tilde{f}_n). \end{aligned}$$

Finally,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{P}_{i_0}(x_{i_0+\frac{1}{2}}) - f_{i_0+1} &= \frac{f_{i_0} - f_{i_0+1}}{2} + \frac{h_{i_0}}{8} (\tilde{f}_{i_0} - \tilde{f}_{i_0+1}) = \frac{f_{i_0} - f_{i_0+1}}{2} + \frac{h_{i_0}}{8} (\dot{f}_{i_0} - \dot{f}_{i_0+1}) \\ &\quad + (A_{i_0,1}^{-1} - A_{i_0+1,1}^{-1}) \lambda_1 (f'_1 - \tilde{f}_1) + (A_{i_0,n-2}^{-1} - A_{i_0+1,n-2}^{-1}) \mu_{n-2} (f'_n - \tilde{f}_n) \\ &= \varepsilon + (A_{i_0,1}^{-1} - A_{i_0+1,1}^{-1}) \lambda_1 (f'_1 - \tilde{f}_1) + (A_{i_0,n-2}^{-1} - A_{i_0+1,n-2}^{-1}) \mu_{n-2} (f'_n - \tilde{f}_n) \\ &\geq \varepsilon - 4|A_{i_0,1}^{-1}| \lambda_1 K_1 - 4|A_{i_0+1,n-2}^{-1}| \mu_{n-2} K_n \\ &\geq \varepsilon - \frac{4\lambda_1 K_1}{12\lambda_1 K_1} \varepsilon - \frac{4\mu_{n-2} K_n}{12\mu_{n-2} K_n} \varepsilon = \varepsilon - \frac{2\varepsilon}{3} = \frac{\varepsilon}{3} > 0. \end{aligned}$$

As a conclusion we remark that the form of the matrix A in (5) and its inverse lead to splines that are close to each other in intervals far from the boundary when different values for the first derivatives are set at the endpoints.

Acknowledgements

We thank the reviewer of [1] who raised the question that inspired this paper.

References

- [1] F. Aràndiga, A. Baeza, D.F. Yáñez, Monotone cubic spline interpolation for functions with a strong gradient, *Appl. Numer. Math.* (2022) 591–607.
- [2] C. de Boor, *A Practical Guide to Splines*, Springer-Verlag, 2001.
- [3] F.N. Fritsch, R.E. Carlson, Monotone piecewise cubic interpolation, *SIAM J. Numer. Anal.* 17 (2) (1980) 238–246.
- [4] D. Kershaw, Inequalities on the elements of the inverse of a certain tridiagonal matrix, *Math. Comput.* 24 (1970) 155–158.
- [5] D. Kershaw, The orders of approximation of the first derivative of cubic splines at the knots, *Math. Comput.* 26 (1972) 191–198.
- [6] J. Stoer, R. Bulirsch, *Introduction to Numerical Analysis*, Springer-Verlag, 1980.